

Voltammetric behaviour of *o*-nitrophenol in aqueous methanol medium at various electrodes

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Abstract : Voltammetric curves of *o*-nitrophenol in aqueous methanol medium for acidic, basic and neutral ranges using B.R. buffer for various concentrations (0.05, 0.1, 0.15, 0.2 mM) and scan rates were obtained. The prominent three reduction peaks corresponding to 3e⁻ change of *o*-nitrophenol was characterized at 0.1 mM concentration in neutral medium at scan rate 90 mV/s. The reversibility of the reaction was also studied by the cyclic voltammetry.

Constant current electrolysis of 0.02 mM *o*-nitrophenol in neutral medium gives *o,o'*-dihydroxyazobenzene at stainless steel (type 316) cathode and counter electrode of same size and material at constant current 1.8 ampere respectively, as a major product which were confirmed by spectral and chemical analysis.

Keywords : Electrochemical reduction, *o*-nitrophenol, cyclic voltammetry, constant current electrolysis, SS cathode.

Introduction

Numerous investigations have been made on the reduction of the aromatic nitro compounds¹⁻³. The nitro group is one of the best electrophores as regards to both ease of reduction and versatility of derived products. Depending on the electrolysis conditions, a great variety of products can be obtained by electroreduction of these substances. Stainless steel electrode have been used widely in our laboratory for the electrochemical reduction of some nitro compounds⁴⁻¹³.

The present work deals with the electrochemical reduction of *o*-nitrophenol at stainless steel electrode, products depending upon the conditions of the reduction. Under the neutral and basic conditions the products are generally arrived at from bimolecular reaction of reduction intermediates^{14,15} and under acidic conditions, the products are generally the hydroxylamine, amine and products derived from their rearrangements¹⁶. Voltammographic studies of *o*-nitrophenol were carried out in acidic, neutral and basic medium. *o*-Nitrophenol is the most readily reducible among the isomeric

nitrophenols. Electrochemical reduction product of *o*-nitrophenol is azo dye (*o,o'*-dihydroxyazobenzene), which is a commercially important dye.

Experimental

Solutions were prepared from A.R. methanol and double distilled water. Reagents such as acetic acid, phosphoric acid, oxalic acid, sodium acetate, potassium chloride and sodium chloride used were of A.R. grade. *o*-Nitrophenol was crystallized from methanol and the crystals (m.p. 44.9 °C) were used. The purity was checked by single spot TLC, IR spectra of *o*-nitrophenol and the product obtained, were recorded and studied to confirm the structure.

Cyclic voltammetric studies were carried out using a three electrode cell assembly having glassy carbon as the working electrode, Ag/AgCl as reference electrode and Pt wire as the counter electrode. Voltammograms of *o*-nitrophenol are recorded in 1 : 1 (v/v) water : methanol at 0.05, 0.1, 0.15 and 0.2 mM concentrations. B.R. buffer was used to maintain desired pH viz. 3.4, 7.0, 9.4.

An Elico Model CL-95 Potentiostat cum Galvanostat coupled with a sweep generator and x-y recorder were used for carrying out controlled current electrolysis. Stainless steel (SS316) electrode was used as cathode. The solutions were stirred by a Remi 2LH hot plate stirrer throughout the electrolysis. H-cell was used as electrolysis cell to carry out constant current electrolysis. FTIR spectra of *o*-nitrophenol and the product was obtained and compared for analysis, identification and characterization.

The preparative electrolysis of 100 ml of 0.02 *M* *o*-nitrophenol was carried out at constant current of 1.8 ampere in neutral medium (pH = 7) for 6 h. The thermometer was kept dipped under the surface of the catholyte. Stirring was done at the maximum speed of the magnetic stirrer. The potential was recorded at the start of the electrolysis and then after 15 min. The temperature was also recorded simultaneously at regular intervals. The electrolysis was terminated when the potential becomes constant with change in time.

Work-up :

After the electrolysis the catholyte was distilled under

reduced pressure and then cooled under ice. It was then filtered and washed several times with taking small portions of water. Each time it was then dried and weighed. A light yellow compound was obtained. The adhering brown colour was removed with activated charcoal in warm methanol. The solution was filtered and allowed to crystallize. Yellow crystals (*o,o'*-dihydroxyazobenzene) were obtained. The purity was checked by singal spot TLC and m.p. 39 °C. The yield of the compound was 90%.

Results and discussion

Cyclic voltammetry :

Cyclic voltammograms were recorded with an applied potential, 0.0 V; intial potential, 0.5 V and final potential -1.5 V at different pH, concentrations and scan rates. Table 1 summarized the voltammetric data for *o*-nitrophenol in acidic, basic as well as neutral medium.

Effect of the pH : Electrochemical reduction of *o*-nitrophenol is easier in neutral medium because of following reasons :

- (i) In acidic medium (pH = 3.4) at concentration 0.1

Table 1. Current-potential measurements in cyclic voltammetry

X-axis = 0.1 V/cm, scan rate = 90 mV/s, applied E = 0.0 V, +E = 0.5 V, -E = -1.5 V, concentration = 0.1 mM

pH	Fig.	Cathodic wave			Anodic wave			Remark
		Wave	Potential (V)	Current (μA)	Wave	Potential (V)	Current (μA)	
3.1	I	I	Not appeared		I	Not appeared		Cathodic wave is irreversible
		II	-0.64	0.05×10^3	II*	Not appeared		
7.0	2(a)	I	-0.18	0.004×10^3	I	-0.12	0.003×10^3	Ist cathodic wave is reversible but others are irreversible
		II	-0.65	0.023×10^3	II	0.11	0.003×10^3	
		III	-1.1	0.027×10^3	III	Not appeared	Not appeared	
9.4	3(b)	I	-0.35	0.004×10^3	I	-0.23	0.003×10^3	Ist cathodic wave is reversible but IIInd is irreversible
		II	-0.95	0.024×10^3	II	Not appeared		

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammograms of 0.1 mM *o*-nitrophenol at pH 3.4 : Y-axis = 0.005 mA/cm, gain = 0.005 mA/V.

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammograms of 0.1 mM *o*-nitrophenol at pH 7 : Y-axis = 0.002 mA/cm, gain = 0.005 mA/V. Scan rate (mV/s) : (a) 90, (b) 80, (c) 70, (d) 50, (e) 40.

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammograms of 0.1 mM *o*-nitrophenol at pH 9.4 : Y-axis = 0.005 mA/cm, gain = 0.005 mA/V.

Fig. 4. Cyclic voltammograms of 0.05 mM *o*-nitrophenol at pH 7 : Y-axis = 0.001 mA/cm, gain = 0.005 mA/V.

Fig. 5. Cyclic voltammograms of 0.15 mM *o*-nitrophenol at pH 7 : Y-axis = 0.005 mA/cm, gain = 0.005 mA/V.

Fig. 6. Cyclic voltammograms of 0.2 mM *o*-nitrophenol at pH 7 : Y-axis = 0.005 mA/cm, gain = 0.005 mA/V.

mM, one cathodic wave (IInd) is appeared which is irreversible as shown in Fig. 1.

(ii) In neutral medium (pH = 7.0) at concentration 0.1

mM, three cathodic waves are appeared. First cathodic wave is reversible but others are irreversible as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 7. Graph between concentration and I_p .

(iii) In basic medium (pH = 9.4) at concentration 0.1 mM two cathodic waves are appeared, in which 1st wave is reversible as shown in Fig. 3.

Hence, in acidic and basic media less defined peaks obtained but in neutral medium prominent peaks are appeared.

(iv) Stainless steel can be easily used as cathode in neutral medium for constant current electrolysis due to its corrosive tendency in acidic media.

(v) For constant current electrolysis, the reduced product *o,o'*-dihydroxyazobenzene was obtained in reasonably good yield (90%) in neutral medium.

Effect of concentration : Three reduction peaks are obtained for neutral medium (pH = 7) as shown in Figs. 2–6. Out of these three waves, first peak is reversible. When the concentration is increased from 0.05 to 0.15 mM, the peak current (I_p) also increases. When the concentration increased further from 0.05 to 0.2 mM, I_p remains constant. This shows that the reaction is adsorption controlled as shown in Fig. 7. Table 2 summarized the voltammetric data for *o*-nitrophenol in neutral medium (pH = 7) at different concentrations.

Effect of scan rates : As the sweep rate was gradually increased to 40, 50, 70, 80, 90 mV/s peak current gradually shifted towards higher values as shown in Fig. 2.

Constant current electrolysis :

The result of the preparative electrolysis at constant current of 1.8 ampere using S.S. electrode led to the isolation of yellow compound *o,o'*-dihydroxyazobenzene, m.p. (39 °C). This is the 3-electron change process in neutral conditions. Purity is checked by single spot TLC. The product is confirmed by the chemical and spectral analysis.

Chemical analysis : The methanolic solution of the product (*o,o'*-dihydroxyazobenzene) turned purple on treating with neutral ferric chloride solution, which confirms the presence of phenolic group in the product.

Table 2. Current measurement with concentration for peak I

X-axis = 0.1 V/cm, scan rate = 90 mV/s, applied E = 0.3 V, + E = 0.5 V, -E = -1.5 V, pH = 7

Concn. (mM)	I_p (µA) →
0.05	1.0
0.1	4.0
0.15	9.0
0.2	9.0

Spectral analysis : The peak due to the nitro group which were originally present in the starting material (*o*-nitrophenol) were no longer found in the products indicating that the reaction being completed.

The aromatic ring was confirmed by a peak in the region 1650–1440 cm^{-1} and the azo derivative was confirmed by a band in the region of 1500–1400 cm^{-1} .

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